

2022, vol. 9, issue 1, 54-66

RESEARCH ARTICLE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6794568>

Implementation of talent management model on Central and East Java province government

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Abstract

This article aims at exploring to what extent the readiness of the HRM agencies at Central and East Java Province in implementing the current talent management policy. This research uses exploitative-qualitative methods through interviews with regional staffing agencies senior officials to discuss policy understanding, institutional capacity, and regional head support in implementing talent management. The results showed that stakeholders' knowledge of talent management policy is sufficient with the implementation plan in line with the established policy. Furthermore, the talent management implementation is more dominant using a strategic-system method than micro-individualistic at the stage of selecting employees, with talent criteria consisting of potential, performance, competence, ethics-integrity, and the provision of competency development programs adjusted to the needs of talents. This research also showed that with the institutional capacity of different human resources managers in both provinces, Central Java Province is relatively more ready to implement talent management than East Java Province. However, the most formidable challenge of the implementation in both regions is to get the support of regional heads so that the process of implementing talent management can run effectively without transactional political intervention.

Keywords: talent, talent management, talent development, public sector

1 Introduction

The Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform (PAN RB) has just issued a policy through the PAN RB Ministerial Regulation No. 3 of 2020 concerning the State Civil Apparatus Talent Management. This policy is a follow-up to Government Regulation Number 11 of 2017 Article 134, which explains that talent management is one of the implementations of the merit system in government agencies and is part of the implementation of civil servant career management. The Minister of PAN and RB (MENPAN, 2020) emphasized that national talent management aims to improve quality and competitive human resources. In general, the main objective of implementing this talent management policy is to realize the right person for the right job in the management of human resources (HR) in government agencies. As emphasized by (Abdalla & Al-Neimat, 2018), "having the right people comes before having the right strategies" emphasizes the importance of human resource placement to encourage organizational progress. The talent management policy is also an embodiment of the statement, "people are our greatest assets in organizations" to achieve organizational performance targets (Hafez et al., 2017). The results of a McKinsey study on the "talent war" in 2001 showed that talented employees (or called a player) contributed to an average

productivity increase of 40% in operational tasks, 49% in general managerial tasks, and 69% in sales tasks.

In public organizations, the apparatus or Civil Servants (PNS) resources are strategic factors that need to be managed so that there is a need for civil servant management. In general, there has been a paradigm shift or perspective on HR management, while the new paradigm of HR management views that HR is an organizational asset or human capital, so it must be managed strategically and proactively (Tetik & Zaim, 2021). The strategic role of human resource management is defined as the link between the implementation of HR management and organizational strategies to improve performance. In its implementation, this strategic role in managing human resources means that HR managers must elaborate on all the capacities possessed by employees or their human resources, to serve as a competitive advantage for the organization. Strategic HR management seems to have become a demand to do. Moreover, the changes in the social environment are related to the characteristics of human resources today, namely the information era that is based on knowledge and technology that can be utilized. In this era, HR is more of a knowledge worker, which means that HR is required to have new knowledge following the ongoing changes (Bethke-Langenegger et al., 2022).

In the institutional aspect, the trend is that the modern organizational structure is getting flatter and leaner, which demands rightsizing that leads to downsizing or downsizing. The implications of these changes in HR and institutional aspects challenge HR managers to find the right strategy to manage HR in their organization. Alternatively, in other words, human resource management with traditional models has begun to shift towards more modern management, which is seen as more adaptive to change. At the bureaucratic level, a shift in the pattern of human resource management for the apparatus or civil servants has also occurred (Akpey-Mensah, 2018). The change in the name of the institution that manages civil servants in Indonesia, namely from National Employees Institution, by eliminating the word 'administration' means that it has undergone a repositioning of roles to become more strategic, not just administrative tasks. Normatively, efforts to support civil servant development by formulating several regulations or policies on civil servant development have not yielded optimal results. For example, the practice of developing civil servants through education and training has not fully met the expectations, namely increasing the professionalism of civil servants. Several phenomena have emerged as a result of changes in the form of bureaucratic reform, including the existence of a civil servant moratorium policy which has an impact on reducing the opportunity to obtain potential new human resources (Aina & Atan, 2020).

Generally, in several organizations or government institutions in the next few years, there will be a 'generation gap' because the number of employees entering the Retirement Age Limit (BUP) tends to increase. This situation is also the case at the structural level. This phenomenon leads to a limited number of qualified human resources. It has become a problem in several government organizations, including how to develop existing human resources to contribute to the organization's superior performance and anticipate changes that occur. This problem will not be solved by carrying out a traditional employee development pattern but requires a strategic development pattern step. The term 'strategic' in this case is interpreted as an integrated and effective pattern. One of the micro dimensions of reform in the management of civil servants is the development of civil servants that pays attention to several new issues, including employee talent or talent. This statement underlies the adoption of the concept of talent management in the management of human resources for the apparatus or civil servants. Talent management is seen as the implementation of an integrated strategy or system, which is designed to improve performance through the process of attracting and selecting, developing, utilizing, and retaining employees who have expertise and talent in order to meet the current and future needs of the organization (Rukunga & Nzulwa, 2018).

The challenges from internal and external every public organization must face requiring the need for HR management that is not just 'doing business as usual' but requires strategic steps. This result is because organizations, including public organizations, will not be able to exist and compete only by using ordinary human resources in the future. Potential human resources are needed as a source of competitive advantage. With many talented human resources, it will produce added value for the

organization to perform superiorly. Another reason relates to external aspects, namely policies in the field of human resources for apparatus or civil servants that in the future will allow openness in the career development of civil servants. The term 'hijacking' HR, which was only possible in profit organizations, is very likely to occur in public organizations. When the demand for qualified human resources allows opening recruitment or promotion and does not have to be filled by internal candidates, this situation has become a discourse in the Draft Law on State Civil Apparatus (RUU ASN), which regulates promotions for the highest structural positions in non-ministerial government institutions from civil servants of all agencies. It can also come from non-civil servants stipulated by a Presidential Decree. The implication is that public organizations that do not yet have a solid human resource development strategy will be prone to be abandoned by the 'talents' they already have. This phenomenon raises a problem about the strategy that must be done to develop talented human resources in dealing with this phenomenon in the future (Pa'wan & Said, 2020).

The studies have tried to analyze the application of talent management in the public sector, such as in the health and education sectors (Erasmus et al., 2017) shows In Indonesia, that only 14% of district governments and 22% of city governments were in the good and very good category in implementing merit system-based HR management/talent management. This result means that there are almost 350 regencies and more than 50 cities where the application of the merit system is still in the wrong and unfavorable categories. Therefore, research on the application of talent management in local governments is fundamental to do. This paper is the result of a qualitative exploratory study that analyzes the readiness of the Regional Employees Institution in Central Java Province to implement talent management in their respective agencies. This study also aims to overview the projected challenges in implementing talent management in local governments. For this reason, this article is written systematically as follows the first part will discuss introduction, literature review, research methods, informants, and instruments used. The second part maps out the findings and key themes obtained from the results of the qualitative data analysis, and discussions. The end of part will show the conclusion and suggestions for further research are presented.

2 Literature Review

Talent management is generally related to training on development strategies, identifying talent gaps, succession planning, and recruiting, selecting, educating, motivating, and maintaining talented employees through various initiatives. Companies that use talent management as a human resource management strategy try to optimize the process of finding, attracting, selecting, training, developing, maintaining, promoting, and transferring employees to be related to the company's main business (Theys & Schultz, 2020). The main objectives of talent management are developing the best top management to face business competition, finding suitable external candidates to fill key jobs, complementing talent between different units, retaining talent through career development opportunities, and expanding the internal talent pool by focusing on several talented employees (Poorhosseinzadeh & Subramaniam, 2022). Schematically, the shift in talent management from individualistic to strategic is described as follows:

Figure 1: Shifting the TM approach from individualistic to strategic
Source: (Gorman et al., 2017)

The picture above shows a shift in the TM approach from an individualistic to a strategic perspective represented by an oval shape. The shift is made from Quadrant I where TM's focus is only on individual "star employees", who are considered competent and professional, to Quadrant III where TM's focus becomes more strategic by paying attention to processes, systems, and resource support so that these "star employees" can develop, contribute, and be a driver of superior organizational performance (Gorman et al., 2017).

Talent refers to two primary meanings: a collection and combination of abilities, competencies, expertise, skills, and commitments that manifest in high employee performance that contributes to organizational performance. In this sense, talent is seen as the aggregate and culmination of a person or group of people who work together to achieve the organization's strategic goals. The second meaning, talent is defined as a specific employee or a specific group of employees who are judged to have the ability, competence, expertise, commitment, which will encourage high organizational performance. For public organizations, the commitment and motivation of employees to serve is sometimes far more important than competence because talents in government agencies are driven by work values to realize common goods for the people. Talent management is an HR management process related to three processes where first, developing and strengthening new employees in the process of first entering the company (onboarding). Second, maintain and develop existing employees in the company. Third, attract as many employees as possible who have the competence, commitment, and character to work for the company (Szabó, 2019).

There are three main approaches when discussing Talent Management where the first approach views talent management as another name for HR management or development. The argument is that both are focused on recruiting the right people for the right jobs at the right time. Both also carry out processes to manage, place, and develop the quality and capacity of these human resources. With this approach, TM is interpreted as re-labeling or re-branding HR management functions to be more up-to-date and credible. However, if analyzed more deeply, this approach does not provide a detailed explanation and complete picture of managing talented employees. As is well known, managing talented employees requires different approaches, techniques, and communication strategies from managing human resources in general (Pauli & Poczowski, 2019).

The second approach defines TM as integrated HR management with a specific focus. In this approach, TM can use the same management tools as HR management, but the focus is different, namely only on a relatively small group of employees who are considered talented. The employee has been evaluated based on current performance or his potential to become a leader in the future. This approach focuses on the formation of talent pools/organizational talent groups filled with selected employees. Organizations recruiting selected employees can be done from internal organizations, as well as competing organizations. The TM process, which is more exclusive, is only intended to manage a small group of selected employees, who are expected to become the driving group for organizational progress (Pauli & Poczowski, 2019).

The third approach sees TM as an organizational strategy to develop competence within the career development framework of talented employees. The focus is on developing the competence and capacity of talented employees by providing enrichment and additional talent pipelines in the context of career development. This third approach brings TM closer to the succession planning process by preparing future organizational leaders. The focus is HR strategic planning to recruit, nurture, and

develop talented employees from the start, providing structured leadership development to place them in a position to replace the organization's top leaders (future leaders) (Pauli & Poczowski, 2019).

The organization must develop a strategy for carrying out the stages and processes of implementing talent management. In various talent management literature in business organizations, the talent management process is generally carried out by recruiting employees outside the organization. HR managers are generally given the task of finding employees who are considered to have a high capacity and have proven their performance in other organizations. These employees are then labelled as talents whom the organization will recruit. In public organizations in Indonesia, talent management practices like this cannot be carried out directly. Moreover, the policies and systems of employee remuneration between government and business organizations are still far different (Iyria, 2013).

For this reason, the talent management process in government agencies needs to be adjusted to the current staffing policy. Instead of recruiting talent from outside the organization, HR managers can map and locate talented employees from within the organization. The talent management process in the company consists of five interrelated processes, namely 1) identifying and selecting talented employees (especially from outside the company), 2) evaluating the competencies and skills of talented employees, 3) reviewing and preparing placement plans, 4) developing and placing and 5) fostering and retaining these talented employees (Ibrahim & Zayed, 2018). According to government HR policies and management, these talent management processes can also be carried out in the bureaucracy but with adjustments. This talent management process can be described as follows:

Figure 2: Talent Management Process Scheme
Source: (Ibrahim & Zayed, 2018)

The description of talent group and development process is described as a pyramid as follows:

Figure 3: Description of the Organizational Talent Pyramid
Source: (Chandratreya & Sajanapwar, 2013)

The figure above shows that four talent groups are the targets and focus of leadership development, namely 1) organizational leadership group, 2) leadership cadres, 3) high potential employees, and 4) all employees. The organization's senior leaders must view the organization's talents, not just a handful of newbies who are positioned as potential leaders. In summary, talent exists in every pyramidal group of organizations, and the task of senior leaders is to develop according to the characteristics and challenges in their position. The groups and their development strategies are in table 1 below:

Table 1: Talent Development by Employee Group

Talent Group	Criteria	Development Strategy
Organization Leader	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> High performance and competence Achievement track record Visionary and build successors 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Cadreization through expert coaching & mentoring Diverse experiences through external insights, assignments, and independent study (as needed)
Leader Cadre	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Middle manager positions in the organization; Competent and performing; Can translate the direction of the organization into the right choices related to finance, human resources, and data; Connecting aspirations between employees and senior managers and vice versa. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Implementing leadership brand Leadership assessment (360-degree assessment); Leadership development, include work experience (70%) and training (30%).
High Potential Employees	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Have a key position in the company; Have an ambition, ability, agility, and achievement. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Offer individual development plans on how to increase contributions to the organization; Guiding leaders and HR professionals to have career information conversations with these employees to help them understand the organization's investment in them.
All employees	All employees who have competencies, commitment, contribution	Building a talent culture by competencies, commitment, contribution

Source: (Chandratreya & Sajanapwar, 2013)

The table above confirms that talent is always present in every job group in the organization. The main task of senior leaders is to create a culture of talent development that is embedded in the mindset of every employee when they are first recruited into the organization. In government agencies, all employees have equal opportunities to develop and contribute to organizational performance. Leaders should map the competence and performance of each employee so that they can determine the talent pool for each group of positions in the organization. Systematic and planned talent development based on fair and transparent organizational competency development systems and policies could create a healthy and constructive talent culture.

3 Method

The method used is qualitative research with an experimental design. Exploratory research is conducted to understand emerging problems or newly implemented policies, and the results do not

provide conclusive results. This research begins with a general idea used as an introduction to more specific issues with an exploratory-interpretative approach (Igwenagu, 2016). This study aims to describe the main themes and approaches used by the Regional Personnel Agency to implement talent management policies in public sector agencies. The final goal is to produce a comprehensive description of the readiness to implement talent management in local governments from the aspect of the meaning of talent management, the availability of resources, opportunities, benefits, and challenges and difficulties that may hinder its implementation.

We used a purposive data sampling method with the selection of research locations in the Central and East Java Provincial Governments based on the merit system in Central Java which showed that most local governments were still in the poor category. Research informants were selected through identification based on the current position, namely senior leaders, both heads of agencies, and heads of fields in the Regional Personnel Agency of local governments. Interviews are conducted by telephone or video-conferencing applications which last approximately 45 to 60 minutes. The interview instrument used is a semi-structured interview, but it can develop according to the dynamics of conversation and question and answer during the interview. The interview instrument focuses on four things, namely:

- a. the meaning of talent, as well as talent management policies;
- b. the purpose of implementing talent management in local governments;
- c. the process and stages of implementing talent management, including its relation to other HR management activities;
- d. the opportunities and challenges of implementing talent management in local government.

Using a qualitative-interpretative research approach, the questions in this interview are aimed at exploring in-depth how the Regional Personnel Agency as the implementing agency implements management policies in local governments and does not express the subjective feelings of the informants. After the data was collected, the interview transcripts were analyzed to obtain key themes using qualitative research methods. The constant comparative technique was used to obtain keywords and themes from the interview data. This technique is done by looking for regularities that appear continuously (recurring regularities) in the informant's words, phrases, or themes. This classification of key themes continues to evolve in line with further analysis of interview data and the results of a literature review on the application of talent management in the Central and East Java Provincial Governments.

4 Result And Discussion

The Meaning of Talent and Talent Management

The terms talent and talent management are still relatively new in policy and human resource management for apparatus in the local government environment. Although the meaning has a good connotation, almost all the informants stated that the meaning of talent is more appropriate for practice in international private companies. However, because it has been stipulated as a policy, all informants stated their readiness to implement it. When asked to explain the informants' understanding of talent, they generally refer to the normative definition contained in the talent management policy. They do not yet fully understand the technical terms of talent management but understanding the meaning of talent and talent management almost all use the exact words as employees who have integrity, performance, competence. Some additional criteria such as having creativity, innovation, ethics, and examples for colleagues.

Table 2: Results of Analysis on the Meaning of Talent and Talent Management

Talent	Talent Management
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees who have integrity and are professional and perform well • Employees with integrity, competence, high performance, creative and innovative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing high-performing employees as potential leaders • The process for identifying, developing, and monitoring selected employees who have

Talent	Talent Management
	talent
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees who have high performance and high competence are measured objectively • Professional, performing, and ethical employees • Employees who are high performing and competent as well as being an example for a work colleague • High-performing and competent employees who obey the rules 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of talented employees so that they contribute to regional progress • Select and manage superior employees to be cadre as OPD leaders in the future
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional employees, showing performance and integrity 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competent and integrity employees • Professional employees and integrity 	

Specifically, informants interpret talent as employees who have high performance supported by behavior, ethics, and integrity. The elements used to measure talented employees are 1) high performance, 2) high competence, and 3) ethics and integrity, which can be seen from the relevant track record, and 4) creativity and innovation that has been implemented. Interestingly, the emphasis on ethics and integrity of several informants to determine whether an employee is talented or not. In terms of the meaning of talent management, several key themes that can be identified are that talent management is carried out to identify potential leaders who will contribute to the progress of the institution and the region. Here the role of the Regional Employees Institution becomes essential to ensure that talent management is carried out by following the principles of applying the merit system. In terms of where talent comes from, all agree that talent in local government must come from internal local government, namely civil servants. The main reason is that talent management is an instrument for career development for internal employees. Thus, talent and talent management have been informally applied in implementing competency development carried out by the Regional Personnel Agency. The problem is that because it is done informally, there is not fully implemented “system” to identify talents, develop them, and provide clear career development opportunities. For this reason, all informants agreed that the Ministry of PAN and RB policy would be a momentum to improve the pattern of career development and competency development carried out by the Regional Personnel Agency.

HR management agencies carry out the talent management process to recruit, develop, and place civil servants who have talent. In general, the talent management process begins with identifying and selecting the talents needed to fill vacancies in the organization. After being selected, the talented civil servants will then be developed following the demands of the competence of the position. If the talent is considered capable, then it is then placed in a position. From the informants' answers to the talent management process, we found that identifying talented employees has been carried out by carrying out competency assessments for civil servants in collaboration with agencies that carry out competency mapping. However, the implementation of the assessment is still partial and does not describe the talent management system. The results of the analysis of the talent management process can be seen in table 4 below:

Table 3: Results of the Talent Management Process Analysis

Talent Management Process	Informants Answer

Talent identification and selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial • Not yet identified critical positions • The practice of competency mapping assessment has been carried out but has not been integrated into the information system staffing
Talent group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determination of talent pool is informal and subjective • There is no transparent talent pool determination system • Consideration of norms and culture of government agencies that promote harmony and communalism
Talent development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submitting to leadership training or technical training • Given additional assignments by the leadership
Talent placement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no planned placement system • Currently placement through PPK

The process of implementing talent management has not been carried out comprehensively by the Regional Personnel Agency. However, all respondents agreed that the implementation of talent management by the Regional Personnel Agency can be said to be still partial. For example, almost all Regional Employees Institutions have conducted assessments for competency mapping for some civil servants. In conducting talent selection, the Regional Personnel Agency requires a performance mapping. The challenge is the analysis of performance data obtained from the results of the employee performance assessment contained in the annual SKP and objectively.

Almost all the informants agreed that the competency mapping activity that the Regional Personnel Agency had carried out could be used as the initial stage to carry out overall talent management. As stated in the policy, the talent management process consists of stages of acquisition, development, retention, talent placement, and monitoring and evaluation. The talent acquisition stage has not been formally carried out, considering the talent mapping process has not been carried out formally in every Regional Personnel Agency. Talent acquisition is carried out to obtain prospective talents who will be needed in the target position. Interestingly, there is a theme that emerges regarding the determination of talent pools that must be adjusted to the norms and culture of the organization. What is meant is that local government employees are generally more based on the values of togetherness (communalism), where harmony and shared feelings are highly valued. While the concept of talent puts forward individualism, namely, talent dares to be different and stands out from his colleagues.

The form of development of employees who are considered to have talent that is currently often carried out by the Regional Employees Institution is by assigning them to take leadership training and other assignments from the leadership. What needs to be underlined is that employees who are considered talented currently still come from structural officials, namely administrators and supervisors, and not many pay attention to certain functional officials. The placement of talent has not been carried out because currently, the placement of prospective leaders is under the authority of the PPK, which is carried out by an internal mechanism in the Position and Rank Advisory Agency (Baperjakat) and the Regional Personnel Agency involved in it. However, all informants hoped that the talent placement process would make the placement of employees in certain positions more transparent and not become a negative issue among employees, primarily related to political intervention from KDP or even members of the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) certain.

5 Opportunities and Challenges of Implementing Talent Management

The prospects for implementing talent management in government agencies are that informants were asked for their views on the opportunities and challenges of its implementation in table 5 following:

Table 4: The Opportunities and Challenges of Talent Management

Opportunities	Challenges
Several Regional Heads support talent management	Get the Regional Head support for the talent management application
Changing the generation of civil servants	Changes in the internal paradigm of employees accepting talent management practices
Application of information technology that supports talent management	Lack of budget support for talent management
The era of openness and the existence of a merit system policy	Talent management must be objective and not follow the politicization of the regional bureaucracy

The most formidable challenge is how to get the Regional Head as PPK to support the implementation of talent management. Several respondents say that the support of the Regional Head was crucial in the implementation of various policies related to HR. Because it is related to the placement and selection of people, the application of talent management is closely related to the authority of the Regional Head. Another challenge is the availability of adequate human resources in BKD, especially those who can map budget needs and activities for talent mapping regarding performance assessment and competency assessment. Availability of assessors is very much needed. Another supporting factor is the availability of an adequate budget, especially in the implementation of mapping. The support of the regional head will be closely related to the availability of the budget. If the regional head supports it so the budget availability will undoubtedly be adequate.

6 Talent Management Development Strategy

Talent management focuses on the coordination and management of various talent management people in the organization. This result is done by conducting research and evaluating each skill, talent management, personality, and character concerning filling vacancies within the company. Everyone has different skills, and the most challenging part of the company is identifying which ones fit into the company culture. Effective HR procedures will be able to recognize these and select from them the most appropriate. Talent management involves many elements, ranging from educational qualifications and skills, previous experience, strengths and additional training they take, abilities, potential qualities and motivation, qualities and personalities. Most companies do talent management in the same way; this can take anything from recruiting and selecting individuals to their placement in the company, training to improve performance, and various schemes to reward high performers. How far companies get involved in talent management depends on the business size and commitment to their employees and their future.

Turnover planning is a basic recipe in business strategy, which makes it possible to give the company the ability to identify high-performing people to plan future rewards. In new management, there must also be a specific career section for employees who want development. It is also necessary to conduct appropriate courses or training to prepare, to prepare them for the new environment. Change planning tools can assist companies in facilitating the identification and development of future talent management in the organization, increase employee commitment, transparent career development, and ease of knowing turnover. A practical solution will reward everyone's achievements, whether or not they perform well in their actions. It will also be helpful to identify who should be awarded. Employee training and development needs require promotion and demotion that are part of all processes, and successful performance solutions should address these elements.

Talent management will not succeed if there is no system used to identify employee performance results. If an employee does something more than his standard, they should be rewarded, otherwise, they may experience a decrease in motivation. Outsourcing the hiring process significantly saves companies money and improves candidate recruitment processes, cutting costs and giving the company something more significant than the market. A high level of talent will lead to a high level of organizational flexibility, productivity, and profit. Scullion & Collings (2010) presented the results of research conducted by McKinsey & Company regarding a survey of more than 120 companies with

12,000 executives and 27 leading companies. The survey shows that managing talent well will lead to good company performance as well. According to Wellins, 2010 (in Andry 2011), there are eight key components to produce effective talent management, namely: (1) business strategy, (2) talent gap, (3) recruitment and promotion, (4) goals, (5) performance, (6) focus, and (7) feedback. By having a group of employees ready to become successors in the talent pool, the company only needs to match the timing of the need for job changes. When that time comes, these potential successors will have no trouble adapting to their new positions. So this will have an impact on the performance of the companies they lead.

7 Discussion

The analysis of the results of interviews with the leaders of the Regional Personnel Agency in Central Java and East Java Provinces described in the previous section provides an overview of the readiness to implement talent management in the two regions as follows:

First, the understanding of the leadership of the Regional Employees Institution in Central Java and East Java Provinces regarding talent management policies is relatively reasonable and quite comprehensive. The criteria used by informants to identify talented employees are elements of performance, potential, and competence, coupled with ethics and talent integrity that upholds the values, customs, and norms that apply. Several informants from Central Java emphasized the criteria of integrity as the primary reference for selecting talented employees because honesty is an absolute criterion for a prospective leader. These four criteria for determining talent align with similar findings in other countries, for example, in a study conducted by Jose Hejase et al. (2016). Kravariti & Johnston (2020) emphasize that talent in government agencies must be based on the principal values of government agencies, namely ethics and integrity of public services. This result is emphasized because public services are very different from business organizations that emphasize profit gain.

Second, regarding the implementation of talent management by the Regional Personnel Agency in Central Java Province, the readiness is still varied. Regional Employees Institutions in Central Java Province are generally more prepared to implement talent management than East Java Province. Central Java Province is more ready to implement talent management than East Java based on the talent management process. This result is supported by adequate institutional capacity such as an assessment center unit and an adequate HR competency development institution. Meanwhile, an informant from East Java Province stated that he was ready to implement talent management by collaborating with other agencies because he did not have an assessment center and an accredited HR competency development institution in East Java. For this reason, considerable budget support is a prerequisite for implementing talent management in East Java. From the talent management approach, informants from both provinces seem to prefer a systemic, strategic approach rather than a micro-individualistic approach. The implementation of systematic strategic talent management requires four stages, namely 1) identification of critical positions in the organization to determine the positions to be filled, 2) implementing an open system for recruitment of talent groups from all employees, 3) providing talent development opportunities that are open to all employees, and 4) assigning talents according to critical positions. While only two things, namely 1, recognize the micro-individualistic approach) the search for individual talents who are considered outstanding from outside the organization, and 2) retention strategies to remain committed to the organization.

Third, the institutional capacity for implementing talent management in Central Java Province can be more prepared than in East Java Province. The institutional capacity in question includes the readiness of human resources, systems, and facilities to support the implementation of talent management. Central Java Province already has an assessment center unit with adequate human resources and a more systematic recruitment system and talent development program. With this condition, Regency and City Regional Employees Institutions in Central Java get better support for implementing talent management. Meanwhile, East Java Province, even though it has HR assessors, has experienced problems in implementing the talent management stages because there is no assessment center unit yet, and the HR competency development agency has not yet been accredited

at the provincial level. This result is understandable because East Java Province is an expansion area of Central Java Province. This finding aligns with what Wolor et al. (2020) and Jayaraman et al. (2018) emphasized: talent management implementation is strongly influenced by strategic environmental factors, such as top management support, stakeholder commitment, and organizational culture readiness.

Fourth, the support of regional heads in the two provinces for the implementation of talent management to avoid local political influence and intervention generally varies. Informants from both provinces stated that formally the leaders in their regions support the implementation of talent management. However, in practice, it varies, from requiring full implementation according to policies to implementing strict talent management by involving regional heads at every stage. However, the common thread is that the recruitment and placement of talented employees must ultimately be in line with the elected regional heads' vision, mission, and policies. Talent ability to translate vision and mission into work programs in critical positions is essential in implementing talent management in both provinces. For this reason, informants in both provinces stated that the ability of the leadership of the Regional Personnel Agency to adapt the application of talent management is very crucial, considering that the Regional Personnel Agency requires financial and budgetary support, reliable information systems, and other supporting facilities so that the implementation of talent management can run optimally.

8 Conclusion

As a result of talent management policies in local governments that are still in the early stages, the results of this study provide several conclusions that can also be used as suggestions for improving the effectiveness of talent management. The concept of talent should be interpreted more than potential and performance criteria. The integrity and ethical requirements of the apparatus should be considered for determining the selection and determination of talent pools. With the strength of communalism and the values of kinship and togetherness in local governments, the application of talent groups requiring competitive and individual values can be complex. Do not let the talent group determined by the PPK later be employees who are considered "close" to the regional head. Institutional capacity support for the implementation of talent management in local governments needs to be improved.

The existence of an assessment center and competent human resource assessors are prerequisites for the effective implementation of talent management. For this reason, the Ministry of PAN and RB should provide incentives for regions that commit to implementing talent management. The strategy for implementing objective talent management with an adaptive approach according to the capacity of the local government will facilitate the implementation of this policy. The exploratory research design was applied to this study. We hope that the initial findings of this research can be used as themes for further research, for example, the effectiveness of the talent recruitment process using the results of the assessment and competency mapping that produces groups of talents and non-talents. Furthermore, it can also be studied about the suitability of development programs based on the results of competency assessments. In addition, the perspectives of internal talent management stakeholders such as talent groups or leadership successor groups can be studied to get a complete picture of the implementation of talent management in local governments.

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